

Distributed Vibration Sensors: Evolution and Applications

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ABSTRACT

The principle of distributed optical fibre vibration sensor is studied. It is shown how distributed vibration sensors (DVSs) use the phase of Rayleigh backscattered light to map vibrations along tens of kilometres of optical fibre. The sensing setup of the DVS used in this study and its operation is explained. Finally, the results obtained from a number of field trials such as submarine-cable condition monitoring and traffic monitoring is presented.

Key words: Distributed Vibration Sensor, Structural Health Monitoring, Geophysical Sciences.

1. INTRODUCTION

The volume of research on distributed optical fibre vibration sensor (DVS) has increased substantially in the past decade. DVS systems owe their rising popularity to their capability of mapping extremely weak vibrations along tens of kilometres of optical fibre under harsh environmental conditions. The sensing principle of distributed optical fibre sensors (DOFS) allows the interrogation unit of such systems to be kept at a safe distance from the area under study while the optical fibre which is used as a sensing probe can be ruggedized to withstand harsh conditions.

The rising demand for DVS systems stems from a number of sectors including structural health monitoring (SHM) in aviation industry and civil engineering, borehole monitoring in geophysical sciences and oil industries, and real-time monitoring of complete rail and road networks for rapid decision and response (Masoudi, 2016).

In this presentation, the principle of distributed optical fibre vibration sensor is explained, the experimental setup used to map vibrations is described, and the results obtained from a number of field trials such as submarine-cable condition monitoring and traffic monitoring is presented.

2. PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION

The principle of operation of the sensor is based on measuring the strain-induced phase variation between the backscattered Rayleigh light from two segments of the sensing fibre as shown in figure 1(a). The relative phase-difference between the backscattered lights from the two segments of the fibre, $\Delta\phi$, is a function of the distance between the two segments, L , and is given by:

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{2\pi n}{\lambda} 2L + \varphi_2 - \varphi_1 \quad (1)$$

Fig 1. a) The effect of external perturbation on the phase of the backscattered light from two separate segments of an optical fibre. b) Experimental setup. DFB: distributed feedback, EOM: Electro-Optic Modulator, IMZI: Imbalanced Mach-Zehnder Interferometer, EDFA: erbium-doped fibre amplifier, PD: photodetector, 3x3: Symmetrical 3-by-3 coupler.

where n is the effective refractive index of the fibre, λ is the wavelength of the probe light, and φ_1 and φ_2 are two random phases.

If the separation between segment *A* and *B* does not change, the value of phase-difference, $\Delta\varphi$, remain constant. Any disturbance that changes the separation between *A* and *B* by ΔL meter results in a change in the phase-difference. The modified phase-difference is given by (Masoudi, 2017a):

$$\Delta\varphi' = \frac{2\pi n}{\lambda} 2(L + \Delta L) + \varphi_2 - \varphi_1 \quad (2)$$

By analysing the changes in the phase-difference as a function of time at each point on the sensing fibre, $\Delta\varphi(x, t)$, the dynamic perturbation along the fibre can be mapped.

In order to measure the phase-difference between the adjacent sections along the sensing fibre, an imbalanced Mach-Zehnder interferometer (IMZI) is employed as shown in the experimental setup of figure 1(b). The setup is an optical time-domain reflectometry (OTDR) system. In this setup, an electro-optic modulator (EOM) is used to form short optical pulses by modulating the output of a distributed feedback (DFB) laser diode. Optical pulses are amplified by an erbium-doped fibre amplifier (EDFA) and launched into the sensing fibre via an optical circulator. The backscattered light is directed towards a secondary EDFA by the third port of the circulator. The amplified

backscattered trace is then fed into the IMZI to mix the backscattered light from adjacent sections of the sensing fibre.

At the output of the IMZI, a symmetric 3×3 coupler is used to avoid interferometer signal fading. The intensity of the light at the three output arms of the MZI is given by (Masoudi, 2013):

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= I_0 [M + N \cos(\Delta\varphi(x))] \\ I_2 &= I_0 \left[M + N \cos\left(\Delta\varphi(x) + \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \right] \\ I_3 &= I_0 \left[M + N \cos\left(\Delta\varphi(x) - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

By using differentiate and cross-multiply demodulation, the phase information can be extracted from the three outputs of the IMZI (Masoudi, 2013).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows the typical output of a DVS system. The outputs can be presented either as a function of time (figure 2(a)) or as a function of frequency (figure 2(b)). Figures 2(a) and 2(b) show the experimental results conducted in the lab by attaching the sensing fibre to a

Fig 2. a) 3D diagram of DVS system output in time domain. b) 3D diagram of DVS system in frequency domain. c) Cable strain level as a function of time following an impact of 4kg wedge shaped steel block measured by the DVS unit. d) Frequency-domain test results for the simulation of train loads from UK 20 m long train vehicle moving at 20m/s. e) Waterfall diagram of traffic flow.

ring PZT. The figures show the location, amplitude and frequency of the strain induced on the optical fibre by the PZT. A comparison between the experimental results obtained by DVS system with the voltage-strain characteristic of the ring PZT used in this test shows that the DVS system can accurately quantify dynamic strains as low as 40ne with a gauge length of 50cm (Masoudi 2017b).

What follows is a selection of experimental results obtain from three different field trials.

3.1 Submarine Cable Monitoring

The cost of subsea cable failure is a major issue in the renewable energy industry. The failures are often mechanically initiated due to the damages sustained during the installation phase when the cable is more likely to experience over-bending or excessive tension. DVS is an ideal tool for condition monitoring of subsea cable during the installation process.

In this study, a 2.5m 3 phase 33kV armoured cable typical used in wind farm arrays was used as a test bench. The test involved releasing a wedge shaped steel block of 4kg with a 90° angle on the test cable while interrogating the embedded optical fibre inside the cable with the DVS system. Figure 2(c) shows the test results for cable impact test. It shows the strain changes of the cable at the point of impact as a function of time and distance. The onset and location of the impact can be clearly distinguished in this diagram.

The rate of strain variation at the onset of the impact exceeds the response time of the sensing unit, mainly due to low repetition rate of the interrogation unit. Following the initial phase of impact, however, transverse beam oscillation can be observed from the 4-th second onwards.

3.2 Railway Monitoring

Another application of DVS system is in structural health monitoring (SHM) of railway track and train wheels. A train in motion applies moving steady loads to the railway track as well as dynamic excitation; this causes track deflections, vibration and noise (Milne, 2017). By analysing the frequency spectrum of the vibration, the condition of railway track and train wheels can be assessed.

For this test, the fibre was attached to the beam which was used to simulate different loads on the track and the sleeper for trains with different length and speed using a hydraulic actuator. The frequency spectrum of the test results for the simulation of train loads from 20m long train vehicle moving at 20m/s is shown in figure 2(d). The spectrum obtained using DVS system

is in good agreement with the results obtained using a geophones and accelerometers (Milne, 2017).

3.3 Traffic Monitoring

Another application of DVS is in intelligent traffic monitoring and management system. Urban transport and mobility is one of the most critical challenges facing large cities both in developing and in developed countries. The larger the city, the greater the complexity of its transport system and the potential for its disruption, particularly when this complexity is not effectively managed. DVS can be used as a versatile monitoring system capable of measuring the speed of individual vehicles, the density of the traffic, and the size of the vehicles. Unlike single point monitoring system such as inductive loops, DVS systems can calculate the inflow and outflow of traffic for any given stretch of road and use this data to estimate the number of vehicles arriving at a junction in advance. This level of information provides an unprecedented insight into how traffic behaves and can potentially revolutionise the way traffic is monitored and managed.

Figure 2(e) shows the waterfall diagram generated by the DVS system. The two diagonal lines in this diagram represent the car passing next to the optical fibre. The position and slope of the diagonal lines can be used to estimate the location speed of the car while the amplitude of the induced strain can be used to estimate the size of the car.

4. CONCLUSION

Detection and quantification of dynamic phenomena has opened a new frontier in distributed optical fibre research. In this work, the principle of DVS is studied. It is shown how the phase of the backscattered Rayleigh can be used to measure extremely small strain variation along the sensing fibre. Finally the application of DVS system in a number of sectors such as subsea cable condition monitoring, railway and train health monitoring, and traffic monitoring was analysed.

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